

Analyzing Elicitation Techniques: knowing the use and challenges to strengthen the requirements phase

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Abstract

Context: Requirements elicitation techniques are critical to helping requirements engineers gain a better understanding of the needs of customers, end users and stakeholders. Currently, there are many RE techniques, bringing possibilities, but, on the other hand, doubts to the technical team about which to use to correctly extract the system requirements. **Objective:** The objective of this study is to provide a list of the most discussed techniques in the literature and compare them with the most presented techniques in projects and case studies to present practitioners with a list of possible techniques for use. Complementary, present the main challenges of requirements elicitation in software development as a way to prepare requirements engineers for the possible problems they will encounter. **Method:** We conducted a Systematic Literature Review (SLR) to identify requirements elicitation techniques and challenges discussed either in literature or in industry and confronted the findings. **Results:** The SLR demonstrated that traditional techniques are still the ones most remembered either in the literature discussions or in the industrial projects. Moreover, some new techniques, such as, Persona and Design Thinking are coming in place helping engineers finding different ways to retrieve the necessary information from users. **Conclusion and Future Work:** The SLR proved to be useful for the community and the investigation will go further analyzing the strengths and weakness of the techniques, as well as combinations of techniques that can together negate each other's weaknesses.

keywords: Requirements Elicitation, Literature and Industry Techniques, Challenges, Agile Process, Software Development

PICOC definition

PICOC terms	Related description
Population	Developers, Analysts, Managers, Customers, Organizations
Intervention	Tools, Methods and Practices on Agile Software Development
Comparison	How to use, pros and cons, challenges
Outcome	Guide presenting the findings, descriptions, examples of using, pros, cons, challenges, suggestions
Context	Papers on literature, since 2011, that presented or reviewed Agile Software tools, methods or techniques

Table 1: PICOC definition

Research Questions

RQ.1: What are the referenced techniques in literature and industry to elicit software requirements that can be used in agile processes?

RQ.1: What are the challenges reported in the literature in using the techniques identified?

Search String

Automatic search string used in each of the digital libraries’.

- Scopus

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TITLE-ABS-KEY ( ( requirement ) AND ( elicitation OR gathering OR specification ) AND ( tool OR technic OR method OR methodology OR practice OR "agile approach" ) AND ( "ASD" OR "agile Software Development" OR "agile requirement" OR "agile practice" OR "agile technique" ) ) AND ( LIMIT-TO ( SRCTYPE , "p" ) OR LIMIT-TO ( SRCTYPE , "j" ) ) AND ( LIMIT-TO ( DOCTYPE , "cp" ) OR LIMIT-TO ( DOCTYPE , "ar" ) ) AND ( LIMIT-TO ( SUBJAREA , "COMP" ) OR LIMIT-TO ( SUBJAREA , "ENGI" ) OR LIMIT-TO ( SUBJAREA , "DECI" ) ) AND ( LIMIT-TO ( PUBYEAR , 2021 ) OR LIMIT-TO ( PUBYEAR , 2020 ) OR LIMIT-TO ( PUBYEAR , 2019 ) OR LIMIT-TO ( PUBYEAR , 2018 ) OR LIMIT-TO ( PUBYEAR , 2017 ) OR LIMIT-TO ( PUBYEAR , 2016 ) OR LIMIT-TO ( PUBYEAR , 2015 ) OR LIMIT-TO ( PUBYEAR , 2014 ) OR LIMIT-TO ( PUBYEAR , 2013 ) OR LIMIT-TO ( PUBYEAR , 2012 ) OR LIMIT-TO ( PUBYEAR , 2011 ) OR LIMIT-TO ( PUBYEAR , 2010 ) ) AND ( LIMIT-TO ( LANGUAGE , "English" ) OR LIMIT-TO ( LANGUAGE , "Spanish" ) OR LIMIT-TO ( LANGUAGE , "Portuguese" ) )
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- **ACM Digital Library**

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[Abstract: requirement] AND [[Abstract: elicitation] OR [Abstract: gathering] OR [Abstract: specification] OR [Abstract: engineering]] AND [[Abstract: tool] OR [Abstract: technique] OR [Abstract: method] OR [Abstract: methodology] OR [Abstract: practice]] AND [[Abstract: "asd" ] OR [Abstract: "agile software development" ] OR [Abstract: "agile requirement" ] OR [Abstract: "agile practice" ] OR [Abstract: "agile technique" ] OR [Abstract: "agile approach" ]]] AND [Full Text: requirement] AND [[Full Text: elicitation] OR [Full Text: gathering] OR [Full Text: specification] OR [Full Text: engineering]] AND [[Full Text: tool] OR [Full Text: technique] OR [Full Text: method] OR [Full Text: methodology] OR [Full Text: practice]] AND [[Full Text: "asd" ] OR [Full Text: "agile software development" ] OR [Full Text: "agile requirement" ] OR [Full Text: "agile practice" ] OR [Full Text: "agile technique" ] OR [Full Text: "agile approach" ]]] AND [Publication Date: (01/01/2010 TO *)]
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- **IEEE Explore**

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("All Metadata":"requirement" AND ("All Metadata":"elicitation" OR "All Metadata":"gathering" OR "All Metadata":"specification") AND ("All Metadata":"tool" OR "All Metadata":"technic" OR "All Metadata":"method" OR "All Metadata":"methodology" OR "All Metadata":"practice" OR "All Metadata":"agile approach") AND ("All Metadata":"ASD" OR "All Metadata":"agile Software Development" OR "All Metadata":"agile requirement" OR "All Metadata":"agile practice" OR "All Metadata":"agile technique")) AND PUBLICATION (2010-2022)
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- **Science Direct** Same used in Scopus base string. The only change was to remove the clause related to limit the subject area, due to incompatibilities of the indexers with this clause.
- **Springer** In this indexer it was necessary to change the clauses not using the "AND" clause which was limiting the results and returning empty in most cases. After replacing to "NEAR" clause the results were more promising.
 ("Requirements" NEAR/5 ("elicitation" OR "gathering" OR "specification" OR "engineering")) NEAR ("technic" OR "technique" OR "method" OR "methodology" OR "practice") NEAR ("ASD" OR "Agile Software Development" OR "agile requirement" OR "agile practice" OR "agile technique" OR "agile approach") AND NOT "medicine" AND NOT "Mathematics" AND NOT "Psychology" AND NOT "Finance" AND NOT "Humanities"

Databases and Journals

Table 2 describing the sources for automatic search in electronic databases based on the search string presented for each indexer and manual search in journals and conferences

Source	Type
Academia	Database
ACM Digital Library	Database
IEEEExplore	Database
Scopus document search	Database
Springer	Database
Science Direct	Database
Requirements Engineering Conference	Conference
ACM IEEE International Conference on Software Engineering (ICSE)	Conference
International Working Conference on Requirements (REFSQ)	Conference
International Conference on Human-Computer Interaction (HCII)	Conference
IEEE Transactions on Software Engineering	Journal
Empirical Software Engineering Journal	Journal
Requirements Engineering Journal	Journal

Table 2: Utilized Sources for the research

Selection Criteria (Inclusion and Exclusion)

Inclusion Criteria	Exclusion Criteria
IC.1. Studies after 2010	EC.1. Studies that present a specific approach
IC.2. Studies related to Agile Software Development	EC.2. Studies published before 2010
IC.3. Studies that describe challenges in general or for any requirement elicitation technique	EC.3. Studies that only provides statistics about a elicitation technique
	EC.4. Duplicated studies

Table 3: Selection Criteria

Quality Assessment

QA	Quality assessment question
QA1.	Does the study describe pros, cons or challenges for using the literature cited practice, method or technique in agile software development?
QA2.	Does the study describe the context of using the cited practice, method or technique in agile software development?
QA3.	Does the study suggest any combination of using the cited practice, method or technique in agile software development?

Table 4: Quality extraction criteria

Score	Definition
Zero (0)	when the study did not mention the information required
A half (1/2)	when the study did mention or reference the information although did not elaborate on it
One (1)	when the study mentioned or referenced, the information also providing at least a brief explanation or examples

Table 5: Quality extraction cutoff score

Revision process

Figure 1: SLR conduction evolution

Selected studies

List of papers per year

Figure 2: Initially accepted papers - per published year

List of papers selected on this study

Id	Paper title
[12]	Information Extraction on Requirement Prioritization Approaches in Agile Software Development Processes
[16]	A Qualitative Study on Non-Functional Requirements in Agile Software Development
[33]	A proposed framework for improved software requirements elicitation process in SCRUM: Implementation by a real-life Norway-based IT project
[24]	Requirements specification for developers in agile projects: Evaluation by two industrial case studies
[21]	Robust approaches, techniques and tools for requirement engineering in agile development
[25]	The role of ethnography in agile requirements analysis
[29]	Infusing Design Thinking into a Software Engineering Capstone Course
[36]	Modelling agile requirements using context-based persona stories
[34]	Agile Requirements Engineering: A systematic literature review
[19]	HCI usability techniques in agile development
[26]	Impacts of agile requirements documentation debt on software projects: A retrospective study
[38]	Investigating the Link between User Stories and Documentation Debt on Software Projects
[22]	Integration of agile practices: An approach to improve the quality of software specifications
[40]	Generating feature model from creative requirements using model driven design

[7]	Handling requirements using FlexREQ model
[1]	Communication patterns of agile requirements engineering
[6]	Automated acceptance test refactoring
[9]	An approach to requirements elicitation and analysis using goal
[3]	Quality requirements challenges in the context of large-scale distributed agile: An empirical study
[23]	Quality of software requirements specification in agile projects: A cross-case analysis of six companies
[13]	The challenges that challenge: Engaging with agile practitioners' concerns
[10]	Requirements engineering: A systematic mapping study in agile software development
[14]	Understanding information needs of agile teams to improve requirements communication
[20]	Mind-mapping: An effective technique to facilitate requirements engineering in agile software development
[5]	A Model of Software Prototyping Based on a Systematic Map
[31]	User and System Stories: An Agile Approach for Managing Requirements in AOSE
[42]	A Requirements Engineering Techniques Review in Agile Software Development Methods
[35]	Key Challenges in Agile Requirements Engineering
[17]	A Systematic Literature Review on implementing non-functional requirements in Agile Software Development: issues and facilitating practices
[2]	Procedural Model of Requirements Elicitation Techniques
[28]	Requirements elicitation techniques: a systematic literature review based on the maturity of the techniques
[39]	Requirements Elicitation: Towards the Unknown Unknowns
[27]	Qualitative comparisons of elicitation techniques in requirement engineering
[41]	Comparison of Various Requirements Elicitation Techniques
[32]	Software Development Lifecycle Models
[43]	Effective Requirements Development–A Comparison of Requirements Elicitation Techniques
[15]	Requirement Elicitation Technique: - A Review Paper
[37]	Revisiting Requirements Elicitation Techniques
[11]	(chapter 5) Requirements Elicitation
[18]	Systematic Review of Requirement Elicitation Techniques
[4]	Ambiguity in user stories: A systematic literature review
[8]	Agile Teams' Perception in Privacy Requirements Elicitation: LGPD's compliance in Brazil
[30]	Quality requirements elicitation by ideation of product quality risks with design thinking

Table 6: Selected primary studies

RQ.1. What are the referenced techniques in the literature and industry to elicit software requirements that can be used in agile processes?

Table containing the studies and their referenced techniques

Ref	Elicitation techniques
[12]	QFA; Use Case; Interview; Questionnaire; Survey; Prototyping; User Stories
[16]	User stories; Story Card; Interviews; Observations; Workshops; Prototyping; Brainstorming
[33]	Brainstorming; Prototyping; Mind mapping
[24]	User Stories; Story Cards; Scenarios
[21]	JAD; Use Cases; Mind Mapping; Story Cards
[25]	FDD; Questionnaires; Interviews; Surveys; Workshops; Data and Documentation analysis; Observation; Ethnography
[29]	Design Thinking; RUP; Prototyping; Persona; Storyboards; Journey Maps
[36]	Persona; User Stories; Storyboards
[34]	User Stories; Mind mapping; Persona; Scenarios; Use Case; Prototyping; Participatory Design; QCD; HCD
[19]	Persona; Scenarios; Storyboards; Prototyping; Ethnography; Observation
[26]	User Stories
[40]	Mind Mapping
[7]	Interview
[1]	Ethnography; User Stories; Story Cards
[6]	TDD; BDD
[9]	Goal based analysis; Scenarios; Use Case
[23]	FDD; Use Case; Interview; Observation; Data and Document Analysis; User Story
[10]	JAD; Prototyping; Mind mapping; User Stories
[14]	Use Case; Persona; Prototyping, Goal model; Rational Unified Process (RUP), User Stories
[20]	Mind Mapping
[5]	Prototyping
[31]	Interview; Questionnaires; Workshop; User Story
[42]	Interview; Use Cases; Focus Groups; Brainstorming; Questionnaire; Prototyping; Observation; Document or Data Analysis
[2]	Interview; Brainstorming
[28]	Interview; workshop; Focus Groups; JAD; QFA; Ethnography; Scenarios; Prototyping; Protocol Analysis; Card sorting; Ontology; Modeling; Goal-based approach; Use Case; Repertory Grids; User Story; Mind Mapping; Group Storytelling
[39]	Use Cases; Interview; Observation; Workshop; Scenario; JAD; Prototyping; Laddering; Ethnography; Participatory Design; AHP

[27]	Brainstorming, Workshop, Prototyping, JAD, Group work, Ethnography, User Scenarios, Introspection
[41]	Interviews, Document Analysis, Questionnaires, Observation, Ethnography, Prototyping, JAD, Brainstorming, Group work, Workshop, User Scenarios, Laddering, CRC
[32]	JAD
[43]	Interviews; Workshop; Focus group; Brainstorming; Protocol Analysis; Ethnography; Observation; Laddering; Scenario; JAD; Prototyping; Storyboards
[15]	Prototyping; Brainstorming; Questionnaires; Laddering; Ethnography; Interview
[37]	Interviews, Document Analysis, Questionnaires; Prototyping; Brainstorming; JAD; Ethnography; Protocol Analysis; Laddering
[11]	Interview, Questionnaire, Introspection, Ethnography, Brainstorming, Prototyping, Legacy system analysis, Scenario, Goal Modeling, Persona
[18]	Prototyping; Document Analysis; Observation; Questionnaires; Interview
[4]	User Stories
[8]	Design Thinking
[30]	Design Thinking

Table 7: Studies and the presented techniques

Word cloud for referred techniques

Figure 4: Pro=Prototyping; Int=Interview; USt=User Stories; Sce=Scenarios; UCS=Use Case; Eth=Ethnography; Obs=Observation; JAD=Joint Application Development; MMp=Mind mapping; Bra=Brainstorming, Que=Questionnaire; Per=Persona; Work=Workshops; Card=Story Cards; Lad=Laddering; SBo=Story Boarding; DT=Design Thinking; PA=Protocol Analysis

- Techniques referenced in 2 papers
 - Data and Documentation analysis
 - Feature-Driven Design (FDD)
 - Goal based analysis
 - Goal model
 - Group work
 - Participatory design
 - Quality Function Assessment (QFA)
 - Surveys
- Techniques referenced in 1 paper
 - Analysis of Legacy Systems (AHP)
 - Test-Driven Design (TDD)
 - Rational Unified Process (RUP)
 - Qualitative/Quantitative Customer-driven Development (QCD)
 - Ontology
 - Journey Maps

- Introspection
- Human-Centered Design
- Storytelling

The complete list of referred requirements elicitation techniques in industry or real-world cases, according to the selected papers.

List of elicitation techniques discussed in Industry

Figure 5: Int=Interview; USt=User Stories; Pro=Prototyping; Que=Questionnaire; UCS=Use Case; Per=Persona; Eth=Ethnography; Obs=Observation; MMp=Mind mapping; DT=Design Thinking; Sce=Scenarios; JAD=Joint Application Development; Bra=Brainstorming, SBo=Story Boarding; DDA=Data & Document Analysis; Par=Participatory design; Sur=Surveys; Jou=Journey Maps; TDD=Test-Driven Design

RQ.2. What are the challenges reported in the literature in using the techniques identified?

Complete list of challenges and the studies that reference it.

Ref	Discussion
[16]	i) insufficiency of the user story format; ii) Reliance on tacit requirements knowledge given by users.

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- [33] i) lack of precise requirements can cause system failure;
ii) scalability limitations towards large-scale projects in agile;
iii) less documentation and quick processing can lead to skipping requirements;
iv) clients that have less knowledge of necessary requirements;
v) clashes among software experts and stakeholders;
vi) requirement prioritization;
vii) communication and coordination with all teams for requirements elicitation.
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- [34] i) lack of allocated time for upfront activities;
ii) difficulty of modularization of the software;
iii) lack of documentation.
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- [26] i) lack of information before jumping into development;
ii) difficulty to prioritize Requirements due to high abstraction level;
iii) lack of Non-functional Requirements Identification;
iv) volatility of requirements;
v) definition of Requirements with a low level of detail;
vi) difficulty to define dependencies between requirements;
vii) difficulty to predict impacts of changes;
viii) problems with the communication and collaboration with users.
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- [38] i) lack of documentation;
ii) requirements prioritization;
iii) lack of identification of Non-functional requirements;
iv) communication and collaboration with users;
v) incomplete design specification.
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- [22] i) customer unavailability;
ii) turnover team;
iii) poor documentation;
iv) communication on remotely distributed teams and clients.
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- [7] i) incomplete requirements;
ii) incomplete domain knowledge;
iii) overlooking tacit assumptions;
iv) definition of system boundaries;
v) ambiguous requirements and inconsistent requirements;
vi) different views of users;
vii) too many “primary“ users;
viii) requirements variability.
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- [3] i) minimal documentation and difficult to document the requirement
 ii) inappropriate architecture when new requirements arise
 iii) customer not available
 iv) difficulties to estimate and plan efforts
 v) requirements prioritization
 vi) difficulties to discover dependencies between sub-systems in early stages
 vii) neglect of quality requirements
 viii) lack of customer's domain knowledge
 ix) team coordination and communication; x) uneven teams maturity;
 xi) difficulties to promote innovative ideas
 xii) hidden assumption.
-
- [13] i) misconceptions and interpretations
 ii) sparse or limited information
 iii) organization culture
 iv) lack of commitment or engagement from stakeholders
 v) distributed teams
 vi) lack of training in specific techniques or practices
 vii) knowledge sharing
 viii) large and complex projects ix) poor documentation x) standard contracts that require upfront specifications
 xi) poor measurement to control project evolution;
Obs. Categories of challenges: organization and management; people; process; and tools related challenges.
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- [14] i) insufficient requirements communication with customer(s);
 i) insufficient requirements communication in teams;
 iii) lapses and rework due to low quality of documented requirements;
 iv) lack of communication of relevant changes to relevant people;
 v) substantial changes of initial estimates of time and cost;
 vi) rework in the architecture design;
 vii) delay in completing the assigned work on time;
 viii) system security, usability or performance is at risk;
 ix) neglecting of non-functional requirements;
 x) communication lapse due to sudden changes in the requirements.
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- [42] i) inadequate understanding of the end user's needs;
 ii) inability to meet changing requirements;
 iii) modules that can not be coupled to work together;
 iv) software difficult to maintain or expand;
 v) late detection of critical faults;
 vi) software of low quality;
 vii) unacceptable software performance.
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[35]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> i) functional or technical dependencies with other teams; ii) independent (detailed) decisions from development team regardless stakeholders; iii) understand the big picture for complex requirements; iv) requirements volatility; v) work out user requirements and quality of use in cooperation with end users; vi) involve stakeholders throughout the whole development process in regular iterations.
[17]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> i) neglecting non-functional requirements (NFRs); ii) misunderstandings regarding user stories; iii) lack of traceability mechanisms of NFRs iv) lack of cost-effective real integration test; v) ambiguous communication process; vi) misunderstanding the architecture drivers between teams; vii) unmanaged architecture changes; viii) hidden assumptions regarding NFRs implementation in inter-team collaboration; ix) moving to Agile with a waterfall mind-set; x) sporadic adherence to quality guidelines by Agile teams; xi) overlooking sources (stakeholders); xii) insufficient knowledge or competencies in the project team.
[2]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> i) lack of participation of user; ii) lack of experience of the analyst; iii) lack of understanding of elicitation techniques.

Table 8: Challenges presented in the studies

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